

Monkeypox

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It is a viral zoonotic infection that can spread from animals to humans. It is caused by the monkeypox virus (Orthomyxovirus). It can also spread from person to person. The disease is called monkeypox because it was first identified in colonies of monkeys kept for research. Thus, it was first recognized in captive primates in 1958 and first identified in humans in 1970 in the Democratic Republic of the Congo.

History of Monkeypox

Monkeypox was first described in 1959 as a primate infection in a Danish laboratory and subsequently was found in eight additional laboratory outbreaks between 1958 and 1968. In August 1970, the first human case was identified in a tropical rain forest village in Equateur province, Democratic Republic of the Congo. Clinically, the disease closely resembles smallpox. Most of patients, exhibit cervical, axillary, and sometimes inguinal lymphadenopathy, which are never observed with smallpox.

Between 1970 and 1995, more than 400 scattered human cases of monkeypox were detected, mainly in Zaire. Investigations revealed that the virus had a natural reservoir in ground squirrels and possibly other rodents, man and monkeys being only incidental hosts. An outbreak in 1996 to 1997 of more than 300 possible cases of monkeypox in central Zaire raised the question at first as to whether human-to-human transfer of virus might occur more frequently than had been thought. However, a simultaneous outbreak of varicella was found to be occurring in the same region, and it was clear that a substantial number of the suspected monkeypox cases were actually varicella cases. In the U.S. outbreak of 2003, most patients with monkeypox reported exposure to wild or exotic mammals (including prairie dogs), and some patients were also household contacts of

affected people. However, no cases of monkeypox could be attributed exclusively to person-to-person contact.

A multi-country outbreak of monkeypox is currently underway in places where the virus has not been typically found before, in Europe, the Americas, Africa, the Western Pacific, and countries of the Eastern Mediterranean. More cases than normal have been reported in 2022 in parts of Africa that have previously reported cases, such as Nigeria, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, and the Central African Republic. WHO is working with all affected countries to enhance surveillance and provide guidance on how to stop the spread and how to care for patients. Monkeypox has been reported in some African countries in the years before this outbreak began. These include Cameroon, the Central African Republic, the Republic of the Congo, Côte d'Ivoire, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, Gabon, Liberia, Nigeria, and Sierra Leone. Some of these countries only had a few cases and others have had persistent or recurrent outbreaks. Occasional cases in other countries have been linked to travel from Nigeria. The current outbreak affecting many countries at once is not typical of previous outbreaks.

Symptoms of Monkey Pox

Monkeypox can cause a range of signs and symptoms. Some people have mild symptoms, others may develop more serious symptoms. Pregnant women, children and immunocompromised persons are at higher risk. The most common symptoms of monkeypox include fever, headache, muscle aches, back pain, low energy, and swollen lymph nodes. This is followed or accompanied by the development of a rash which can last for two to three weeks. The rash can be found on the face, palms of the hands, soles of the feet, eyes, mouth, throat, groin, and genital and/or anal regions of the body. The number of lesions can range from one to several thousand. Lesions begin flat, then fill with liquid before they crust over, dry up and fall off, with a fresh layer of skin forming underneath.

Symptoms typically last in two to three weeks and individual recovers on their own or with supportive care for pain or fever. Newborn babies, children and immunocompromised may exhibit more serious symptoms and death from monkeypox.

Person remains infectious until all of the lesions have crusted over, the scabs fallen off and a new layer of skin has formed underneath.

Complications from monkeypox include secondary skin infections, pneumonia, confusion, and eye problems. The mortality with monkeypox ranges between 1% to 10%.

Transmission of monkeypox

Monkeypox spreads from person to person through close contact with patients having rash, or through face-to-face, skin-to-skin, mouth-to-mouth or mouth-to-skin contact, including sexual contact. The persons with monkeypox are infectious until all of their lesions have crusted over, the scabs have fallen off and a new layer of skin has formed underneath. Environments can become contaminated with the monkeypox virus, for example when an infectious person touches clothing, bedding, towels, objects, electronics and surfaces. It is also possible to become infected from breathing in skin flakes or virus from clothing, bedding or towels. This is known as fomite transmission.

Ulcers, lesions or sores in the mouth can be infectious, meaning the virus can spread through direct contact with the mouth, respiratory droplets and possibly through short-range aerosols. Possible mechanisms of transmission through the air for monkeypox are not yet well understood and studies are underway to learn more.

The vertical transmission can also take place from pregnant mother to the fetus, after birth through skin-to-skin contact, or from a parent with monkeypox to an infant or child during close contact.

Although asymptomatic infection has been reported, it is not clear whether people without any symptoms can spread the disease or whether it can spread through other bodily fluids. Pieces of DNA from the monkeypox virus have been found in semen, but it is not yet known whether infection can spread through semen, vaginal fluids, amniotic fluids, breast milk or blood. Research is underway to find out more about whether people can spread monkey pox through the exchange of these fluids during and after symptomatic infection.

Monkeypox can spread from animal to human by physical contact with an infected animal. The reservoirs of virus for animals are rodents and primates. squirrels and other rodents, are thought to be the reservoir hosts for this virus. The virus is found in tropical rain forest areas of west and central Africa. Because vaccination with vaccinia virus gives partial protection against monkey pox. The risk of catching monkey pox from animals can be reduced by avoiding unprotected contact with wild animals, especially those that are sick or dead (including their meat and blood). In endemic countries where animals carry monkey pox, any foods containing animal meat or parts should be cooked thoroughly before eating.

People who were vaccinated against smallpox may have some protection against monkey pox.

Vaccination against monkeypox

A vaccine was recently approved for preventing monkey pox. Some countries are recommending vaccination for persons at risk. Smallpox, vaccine may also be useful for monkey pox. Mass vaccination is not recommended at this time.

Prevention against monkeypox

- One should protect from monkeypox by avoiding close contact with infected or suspected or confirmed monkeypox, animals/humans.
- Clean and disinfect contaminated environments with the virus from infected man or animal with monkeypox.
- Isolate the infected one from healthy, the infected individuals should avoid sexual contact for 12 weeks after recovery.
- The infected person keeping in mind the severity of disease gets isolated at home in a separate room, or may be admitted to the hospital.
- Use a separate bathroom, if not possible clean after each use.
- Use separate utensils, towels, bedding and electronics.
- Keep separate bedding, clothes and towels etc. to the washing machine and wash them with hot water > 60 degrees).
- Provide good ventilation.
- Encourage cleaning of hands regularly with soap and water or with alcohol-based hand sanitizer.
- Take plenty of lukewarm water, eat well, and get enough sleep.
- People with monkeypox should avoid scratching their skin and take care of their rash by cleaning their hands before and after touching lesions and keeping skin dry and uncovered (unless they are unavoidably in a room with someone else, in which case they should cover it with clothing or a bandage until they are able to isolate again). The rash can be kept clean with sterilized water or antiseptic. Saltwater rinses can be used for lesions in the mouth, and warm baths with baking soda and Epsom salts can help with lesions on the body. Lidocaine can be applied to oral and perianal lesions to relieve pain.
- European Medicines Agency recommend to treat monkeypox with tecovirimat of smallpox antiviral drug.
- If you cannot avoid being in the same room as someone else or having close contact with another person while isolating at home, then do your best to limit their risk by:
 - Avoiding touching each other

- Cleaning your hands often
- Covering your rash with clothing or bandages
- Opening windows throughout the home
- Ensuring you and anyone in the room with you wear well-fitting medical masks
- Maintaining at least 1 meter of distance.

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